

Geoprivacy Open Data – A New FAIR Personal-Level Mobility Dataset for Research and Innovation

Juha Oksanen*, Anna Brauer **, Ville Mäkinen*

* Finnish Geospatial Research Institute, National Land Survey of Finland

** Chair of Geoinformatics, Dresden University of Technology, Germany

Abstract. This paper presents Geoprivacy Open Data - an open personal-level movement dataset collected using the Geoprivacy platform. The Geoprivacy platform allows cyclists, runners and pedestrians to contribute GPS and other GNSS tracking data for scientific research and for free use in the open data repository. To ensure compliance with GDPR, Geoprivacy Open Data is sanitized using five privacy protection methods: regional and population density -based filtering, removal of explicit identifiers, site-dependent trajectory truncation, and time shifting. The paper provides details on the accumulation and spatial distribution of the data, and outlines potential uses given its spatio-temporal characteristics.

Keywords. GPS, GNSS, trajectory data, cycling, privacy-preserving data publishing, VGI, open data

1. Introduction

In recent years, it has been estimated that transport was responsible for about 25% of the EU's CO₂ emissions, of which more than 71% originates from road transport (EU 2024). The EU Commission's Climate Target Plan aims to reduce greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions by at least 55% by 2030, setting the stage for Europe to achieve climate neutrality by 2050. Achieving this ambitious goal requires a fundamental shift in how personal mobility is approached, along with the development and adoption of disruptive technologies that enhance resource efficiency and improve the cost-effectiveness of road infrastructure investments. One such innovation is the utilization of open personal-level movement data in a way that safeguards privacy. By using the term *personal-level movement data*, we emphasize

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that the data is not personal data as defined today by the EU's General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) (EU 2016).

Investing in infrastructure that supports walking and cycling is essential to fostering safer and more inclusive cities. To truly revolutionize urban mobility, it is crucial to create a supportive environment for all individuals, not just cycling enthusiasts (Aldred et al. 2016). Given limited public resources, investments should be directed toward cost-effective infrastructure solutions. One underutilized yet valuable data source for planning is volunteered geographic information (VGI), where pedestrians and cyclists use GNSS-enabled devices to track their movements (Nelson et al. 2021). Despite challenges like participation inequality (Bergman & Oksanen 2016), VGI data holds immense potential (Oksanen et al. 2015; Brauer et al. 2021).

Building on this foundation, we explored solutions for sharing anonymized personal location data as open data. Our initial step was a survey assessing attitudes toward data sharing and privacy concerns (Jokinen et al. 2021). Results indicated a positive inclination toward contributing tracking data, provided strong privacy protections were in place. Participants were primarily motivated by potential improvements in biking and pedestrian infrastructure but sought more immediate feedback. Encouraged by these findings, we developed a service allowing citizens to donate their tracking data in a fully anonymized form (Mäkinen et al. 2022a, 2022b; Brauer et al. 2023). In May 2023, we launched the pilot service via the Geoportti Research Infrastructure.

In this paper, Geoprivacy Open Data collected using the Geoprivacy platform will be extensively presented. We provide details on the accumulation and spatial distribution of the data and outline potential uses of the data, considering its specific spatio-temporal characteristics. In our final presentation, we will also compare its characteristics with other similar open datasets.

2. What is Geoprivacy Open Data?

The Geoprivacy platform allows cyclists, joggers, and pedestrians to contribute GPS and other GNSS tracking data for scientific research. Geoprivacy Open Data is an anonymized tracking dataset in GPX format, created from voluntarily donated personal mobility data. At the moment, the service supports donations only in GPX- and FIT-formats. Anonymization ensures that all direct and indirect identifiers are removed while preserving the original data as much as possible. These raw data donations are collected through the Geoprivacy platform: <https://geoprivacy.fi/>.

The platform updates data hourly, while frozen monthly and yearly versions—complete with exhaustive metadata, persistent identifiers, and access—are available via the [Etsin Fairdata service](#).

2.1. Data processing and anonymization

When the raw trajectory data arrives at the Geoprivacy platform’s backend for processing, we use a total of five different methods to ensure the service’s GDPR compliancy and to protect the privacy of users:

1. Filtering with the region of Finland

This method makes a first quick check that the donated material is located in Finland. Although EU legislation should be harmonized, this check ensures that the guidance provided by the Finnish lawyers consulted during the service development is certainly valid in the area covered by Geoprivacy Open Data.

2. Removal of explicit identifiers

The most obvious action for donated data is to remove all direct and explicit identifiers, i.e., email address and internal user ID. This is necessary because all data submitted via the Geoprivacy platform is associated with a user ID. For security reasons, the delivery of data requires the creation of a user account and the provision of a valid email address.

3. Filtering by population density

Low population density significantly increases privacy risks. Finland has very large areas with very low population density and, to be on the safe side, donations made in low population density areas (less than 5 inhabitants per square kilometre) are not accepted in the Geoprivacy Open Data.

4. Trajectory Truncation

Using the Site-dependent Trajectory Truncation algorithm (Brauer et al. 2022), we truncate trajectories based on nearby buildings at trajectory endpoints and any prolonged pauses along the route. This method requires detailed building data for the specific geographical region, limiting trajectory donations during the pilot phase to Finland’s densely populated areas.

5. Time Shifting

After truncation, trajectories undergo temporal shifting (Brauer et al. 2023). The start time of each trajectory is aligned to the nearest predefined time, set at 6-hour intervals throughout the day. In addition, the day of the month is changed to the first same weekday of that month. This approach significantly reduces the risk of linking obfuscated trajectories to external datasets, such as surveillance camera recordings.

3. Geoprivacy Open Data Facts and Figures

At the time of writing this work in progress paper, four frozen versions of the Geoprivacy Open Data have been published (2023/09, 2023/10, 2023/11, and 2024/11). After the fourth release, the dataset will only be published as an incrementally accumulating dataset, so the persistent identifier and metadata of the different temporal versions will remain common.

Looking at the accumulation of data, we see that between August 2023 and November 2024, the number of tracks collected exceeds 2500 (Figure 1a) and the total length of routes exceeds 30,000 km (Figure 1b). The total number of contributors has been <10 throughout the history of Geoprivacy Open Data. When we look at the regional distribution of the data (Figures 2a and 2b), by far the largest part of the data is from the Helsinki Metropolitan Area, but there is also data from other cities, such as Hämeenlinna, Tampere, Vaasa, Joensuu and Oulu.

Figure 1. Accumulation of (a) number of tracks and (b) total length of the Geoprivacy Open Data Aug 2023 – Nov 2024.

4. Benefits of Geoprivacy Open Data

The Geoprivacy Open Data benefits, for example, urban planners, scientists, and industry professionals interested in leveraging detailed mobility data for research and innovation. A typical characteristic of data collected by crowdsourcing is participation inequality (e.g. Oksanen et al. 2015) and the biases it causes. In this data, these characteristics are accentuated by the low number of contributors and must be taken into account in the applications. The dataset is best suited for use cases where the number of distinct contributors is not a key attribute. A good example of such a use case is the analysis of cycling fluency (e.g. Brauer et al. 2021).

Figure 2. (a) The number of tracks and (b) the total length (km) of the Geoprivacy Open Data in 10*10km² grid.

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References

- Aldred R, Woodcock J, Goodman A (2016) Does More Cycling Mean More Diversity in Cycling?, *Transport Reviews*, 36:1, 28-44, <https://doi.org/10.1080/01441647.2015.1014451>.
- Bergman C, Oksanen J (2016) Estimating the Biasing Effect of Behavioural Patterns on Mobile Fitness App Data by Density-Based Clustering. In: Sarjakoski, T, Santos, M.Y., Sarjakoski, L.T. (Eds.). *Geospatial Data in a Changing World. Selected papers of the 19th AGILE Conference on Geographic Information Science. Lecture Notes in Geoinformation and Cartography*. Springer International Publishing.
- Brauer A, Mäkinen V, Oksanen J (2021) Characterizing cycling traffic fluency using big mobile activity tracking data. *Computers, Environment and Urban Systems*, 85, 101553. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compenvurbsys.2020.101553>.
- Brauer A, Mäkinen V, Forsch A, Oksanen J, Haurert JH (2022) My home is my secret: concealing sensitive locations by context-aware trajectory truncation. *International Journal of Geographical Information Science*, 1-29. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13658816.2022.2081694>.

- Brauer A, Mäkinen V, Oksanen J (2023) Human mobility tracks as FAIR data: Designing a privacy-preserving repository for GNSS-based activity tracking data, *AGILE GIScience Ser.*, 4, 21, <https://doi.org/10.5194/agile-giss-4-21-2023>.
- EU (2016) REGULATION (EU) 2016/679 OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation). <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/HTML/?uri=CELEX:32016R0679&from=FI>.
- EU (2024) CO2 emissions from cars: facts and figures (infographics). <https://www.europarl.europa.eu/topics/en/article/20190313STO31218/co2-emissions-from-cars-facts-and-figures-infographics>
- Jokinen V, Mäkinen V, Brauer A, Oksanen J (2021) Would Citizens Contribute their Personal Location Data to an Open Database? Preliminary Results from a Survey. In 16th International Conference on Location Based Services (p. 171).
- Mäkinen V, Brauer A, Oksanen J (2022a) Building an Open Personal Trajectory Repository. Proceedings of the Fourteenth International Conference on Advanced Geographic Information Systems, Applications, and Services (GEOProcessing 2022), Porto, Portugal, pp. 58-61.
- Mäkinen V, Brauer A, Oksanen J (2022b) A pilot service for sharing obfuscated personal level location data. Proceedings of the 17th International Conference on Location-Based Services (LBS Conference 2022), pp. 163-165.
- Nelson T, Ferster C, Laberee K, Fuller D, Winters, M. (2021) Crowdsourced data for bicycling research and practice. *Transport reviews*, 41(1), 97-114.
- Oksanen J, Bergman C, Sainio J and Westerholm J (2015) Methods for deriving and calibrating privacy-preserving heat maps from mobile sports tracking application data. *Journal of Transport Geography*, 48, pp.135-144.